

SMART Items

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

A method to help **set clear, decisive, and explicit actions** during and after meetings. You will need to have your action items identified before you can implement this method.

Benefits

This will clarify which actions need to be undertaken by whom, by when, in which format and to which extent. By describing action items in this joint manner, you will be able to push your MA proposal development further and ensure clarity on the co-ownership of the final result.

Practical recommendations

At the end of a/each meeting, go through the actions identified. For each action, check whether the action item is noted down in a '**SMART**' way for everyone in the consortium.

AN EXAMPLE:

One action identified during the meeting was that every organisation in the consortium needs to share their average monthly salary cost with the coordinator. At the end of the meeting, the facilitator picks this action item back up and asks the group to make it SMART:

- **SPECIFIC:** The partners need to share their average monthly salary rate with the coordinator in order for the budget to be made up. It is important that all partners know what an average monthly salary rate means under the Horizon Europe framework and how they can calculate this should they not know.
- **MEASURABLE:** This task will be successfully completed after each partner sent this information via e-mail to the contact person at the coordinating organisation.
- **ASSIGNABLE:** At the level of each organisation, the key contact person is responsible for completing this task. At the level of the consortium, the contact person at the coordinating organisation is responsible for the collation of the information.
- **REALISTIC:** As this is sensitive information, the consortium decides to work via direct e-mailing and have one collated file controlled by the coordinator.
- **TIME-BOUND:** All partners agreed that 2 weeks is a reasonable deadline for this information to be sent.

Credit: This workshop format is sourced from FunRetrospectives (<https://www.funretrospectives.com/>)

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agendas, expectations and results

Be comfortable with co-ownership and responsibility of tasks, results and outcomes

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[SMART Items by FunRetrospectives](#)

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